

Underlying Meaning of Probability in Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis Distributions

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 2, 2025

Probability is a measure of the uncertainty of a result, but we argue that there is more involved in the case of the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions. In fact, it is not correct to simply list a Kaniadakis distribution because there are both $\exp k$ and Gaussian- k distributions, which is directly related to the topic of this note. In particular, we suggest that probability distribution, instead of simply being described as $p(e_i/T)$, is actually a function of the conserved quantity in the problem, although matters are more complicated than this in the Kaniadakis case. Thus, it is no accident that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, or the Tsallis $\exp-q$ or Kaniadakis $\exp-k$ involve linear expressions in $-e_i/T$ to a power (in the latter two cases). The Kaniadakis $\exp-k = (\sqrt{1+kke_i e_i/TT})^{-ke_i/T}$ power $1/k$ and so it is the $-ke_i/T$ term which demonstrates the conserved quantity, but we will show how all three approaches identify with a conserved quantity. The a priori conserved quantity is $E = \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ or $E = \sum_i p(e_i)$ power q e_i in the Tsallis case. If the conserved quantity $\langle EE \rangle$, then $e_i^* e_i$ is used and leads to a different distribution.

This leads to the next question. Probability $p(e_i)$ represents the uncertainty associated with e_i , and one often wishes to have maximum uncertainty. For example, a uniform distribution, by not distinguishing between any specific outcomes, maximizes uncertainty, but there is no concept of a conserved quantity. We have argued that one requires $p(e_i)$ to explicitly show the conserved quantity in its functional form and so probability unfortunately cannot be the sole measure of uncertainty. In fact, it carries information about the conserved quantity, be it e_i or $e_i^* e_i$ or some other moment or function $f(e_i)$. Thus, it seems that one is forced to introduce a second uncertainty function which should be maximized (remove as much information), but should be subject to the two constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i)$, where $f(e_i)$ is the constraint function, be it e_i or $e_i^* e_i$ etc. The key assumption which seems to arise is that instead of having $F(\text{all } p(e_i)\text{'s})$, one has an uncertainty function which is additive. I.e. $\sum_i g(p(e_i))$ so that one may link each $g(p(e_i))$ with the $f(e_i)$ information. In other words, the idea of this maximization is to treat each $dp(e_i)$ as independent in a sense in that the overall coefficient of $dp(e_i)$ is 0 for each i even though $\sum dp(e_i) = 0$ meaning that in general $dp(e_i)$'s are not independent. This approach allows one to force $p(e_i)$ to be a function of the constraint variable e_i or $e_i^* e_i$ etc or function $f(e_i)$, while at the same time maximizing a loss of information.

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases, this approach leads to writing $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ (which is general because $p(e_i) > 0$). We argue that this step is key to forcing $p(e_i)$ to include the form of the conserved quantity $f(e_i)$, but that is not the whole picture. A second key idea of these two distributions is that they match $d/dp(e_i) g(p(e_i)) dp(e_i)$ directly to the constraints number $= \sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i)$ (or $p(e_i)$ power q in the Tsallis case) and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. The Kaniadakis case also makes use of $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ and also links the first derivative term: $dp h(p(e_i))$ to the constraint $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = \text{number}$, but does not link the second derivative term, $p dh/dp$ to these two constraints, showing that one may functions: \sum

over i $q(p(e_i)) dp(e_i) = 0$ without this being a linear combination of: $\sum_i (c_1 e_i + c_2) dp(e_i)$. In terms of the probability demonstrating the $f(e_i)$ constraint piece, this is enforced in all three cases by $h(p(e_i)) = f(e_i) * \text{Lagrange multiplier}$ where Lagrange multiplier = $-1/T$.

The Meaning of Probability

Classical probabilities are known to add to 1, i.e. $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ ((1)).

Probabilities represent uncertainty in a problem. If one has a set of outcomes and wishes to have maximum uncertainty, then one cannot have any special information about any of these outcomes and one has the uniform distribution:

$$p(i \text{ outcome}) = 1 / \text{Number of outcomes} \quad ((2))$$

In general, however, one has conserved quantities in a problem which are physical in nature. For example, a gas consists of N particles, each has a kinetic energy e_i if there is no potential and there is a total energy E . In such a case,

$$E = \sum_i p(e_i) e_i \quad ((3)) \quad (\text{This is a physical idealization.})$$

((3)) is usually an approximation because one allows e_i to take on all values from 0 to infinite.

((3)) is not the only a priori constraint one may have. One could have:

$$\langle EE \rangle = \sum_i e_i * e_i p(e_i) \quad ((4))$$

In such a case, the total average energy is not conserved, but the $\langle E^2 \rangle$ is.

One may at first think that $p(e_i)$ describes a scenario with any constraint, be it linked to e_i , $e_i * e_i$ or some function $f(e_i)$. We suggest that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis scenarios, this is not the case. The probability $p(e_i)$, in addition to describing uncertainty, must also describe physical information present and this means the constraint function $f(e_i)$. Thus, we argue that it is not sufficient to have a single function $p(e_i)$ describe the uncertainty in a system. One requires a second one, which may be maximized (loss of information to create a probability) subject to constraint associated with conserved quantities.

$$\text{Probability } \sum_i p(e_i) = 1$$

We first note that $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ is associated with a conserved quantity, namely probability. This is why: $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$. We suggest that other constraint in typical gas

problems should also include conserved quantities such as $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ if E is the conserved quantity.

The Notion of Entropy

Probability is an uncertainty function/measure, but also a measure of the conserved quantity, we have argued. One must have a process which is linked with maximum loss of information subject to constraints which ensures that $p(e_i)$ is a function of the conserved quantity. This seems to suggest that it is too general to write:

Uncertainty function(all $p(e_i)$'s) ((2))

Instead, one must have:

Uncertainty function = $\sum_i g(p(e_i))$ ((3))

((3)) ensures that the overall uncertainty is a sum of the uncertainty of each $p(e_i)$, but allows one to link each $g(p(e_i))$ to its constraint piece $f(e_i) p(e_i)$ and $p(e_i)$, thus forcing $p(e_i)$ to be a function of $f(e_i)$. In other words, one maximizes each:

$g(p(e_i)) - b_1 p(e_i) - b_2 f(e_i) p(e_i)$ ((4))

As if it were an independent piece, even though $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ shows that the $p(e_i)$ changes are linked.

One way to have $p(e_i)$ directly become a function of $f(e_i)$ is the approach used for the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis scenarios. In these cases, one may write without any loss of generality because $p(e_i) > 0$:

$p(e_i) h(p(e_i)) = g(p(e_i))$ ((5)) and maximize ((4)) using this form.

The trick is to force $dp(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ to map to $f(e_i) dp(e_i)$ and $p(e_i) dh/dp dp(e_i)$ to $dp(e_i)$.

This is done for the MB, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases.

Then, one has:

Maxwell-Boltzmann: $h(p(e_i)) = f(e_i)$ and $dh/dp(e_i) p(e_i) = b_1 = -1/T$ or $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((6))

Here $-b_2 f(e_i) = -e_i/T$

Tsallis Case: The constraint is: $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$ so:

$$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i) \text{ power } q \quad dh/dp(e_i) = b_1 = -1/T$$

$$\text{This means that } h(p(e_i)) = \text{constant} + p(e_i) \text{ power } (1-q) \quad ((7))$$

The Kaniadakis case is a little different. One may still write $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ without any loss of generality and:

$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ if E is the conserved quantity, but if $\langle EE \rangle$ is, then one has $-e_i^2/T$ and obtains Gaussian-k instead of exp-k.

The key point here is that one is forcing the form of the constraint on $p(e_i)$ through $h(p(e_i)) = -1/T f(e_i)$, where $f(e_i)$ is the constraint function. The difference with the Kaniadakis case is that the second varied term: $p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i)$ is not linked to the two constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i) = \text{number}$.

Writing; $\sum_i p(e_i) h(p) = -\sum_i e_i/T p(e_i)$ means that if one takes $d/dp(e_i)$ of both sides:

$$\sum_i dp(e_i) \{ h(p(e_i)) + p(e_i) dh/dp \} = 0 = \sum_i (-e_i/T) dp(e_i) \quad \text{because of the constraint.}$$

$$\text{Now, } h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad (\text{for } f(e_i) = e_i) \quad ((8)) \quad \text{so one must have:} \quad \sum_i p(e_i) dh/dp dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((9))$$

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases, $dh/dp * p = \text{constant}$ is sufficient for having ((9)) add to zero and this matches a constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$.

The $h(p(e_i))$ term now matches the energy constraint term $-e_i/T$, but any result which allows ((9)) to hold is acceptable. Following the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis recipes, one might expect:

$$p(e_i) dh/dp = -\text{constant}_1 * e_i/T + \text{constant}_2 \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Combining } ((8)) \text{ and } ((10)) \text{ yields:} \quad h = \text{constant}_3 + p dh/dp / (-\text{constant}_1) \quad ((11))$$

If one considers: $h = 1/(2k) \{ p \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k \}$ ((12)) (so that one still uses a power law, but differs from the Tsallis distribution) then:

$$H = c_3 + \frac{1}{2} (p \text{ power } k + p \text{ power } -k) c_1 \quad ((13))$$

((12)) seems incompatible with ((13)) and so this calls into question ((10a)).

In particular, if one uses a power law form: $p(e_i) = \text{function}(e_i) \text{ power } 1/k$, then ((8)) leads to:

$$p(e_i) = (\sqrt{1 + k e_i / T} - k e_i / T) \text{ power } 1/k \text{ (unnormalized)} \quad ((10b))$$

The LHS of ((13)) is $-e_i/T$, while the RHS is:

$$C_3 + .c_1 k \sqrt{1 + k e_i / T} \quad ((10c))$$

Thus, ((13)) does not hold and one cannot use the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis approach of matching $p(e_i) dh(p(e_i))/dp(e_i)$ with a constraint term. One needs a different function, whose sum yields zero.

To find this new object, consider: $\sum_i dp(e_i) h = 0$ so $\sum_i dh/dp p dp(e_i) = 2 \sum_i p \text{ power } k \text{ constant } dp(e_i)$

$$\text{Now: } \sum_i d/d(p(e_i)) (p h) dp(e_i) = 0 = \sum_i h dp(e_i) + \sum_i p dh/dp dp(e_i) \quad ((14))$$

The first term on the RHS of ((14)) is 0, so the second term must also be 0. One may use ((12)) and ((8)) to find a solution for $p(e_i)$, but this solution must ensure that the second term on the RHS of ((14)) is 0.

In other words, instead of matching $p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i)$ to either the $\sum f(e_i) p(e_i) = \text{number}$ or $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ constraints, one has instead:

$$\sum_i (p(e_i) \text{ power } k + p(e_i) \text{ power } -k) = 0 \quad ((15))$$

In ((15)), one is interested in the overall sum and not in the value of a single term in the sum. The Kaniadakis case seems to require stronger constraints than simply the two linked with (e_i) and $p(e_i)$ because:

$$(p(e_i) \text{ power } k + p(e_i) \text{ power } -k) / (2k) = \sqrt{1 + k e_i / T} \quad ((16))$$

((16)) is a positive number, and a priori it is not clear that ((16)) multiplied by $dp(e_i) = 0$. Rather, there seems to be a $\sum_i ((16)) * dp(e_i) = 0$ condition which must be considered if the Kaniadakis approach is to hold.

One may note that one now has two terms in ((10b)). One is the linear $-e_i/T$, linked to e_i being a conserved quantity, but there is an additional $\sqrt{1+kke_i/T}$ due to the condition linked to ((16)) and so care must be taken in resolving what the conserved variable is. One may see clearly that it is e_i from $h(e_i) = -e_i/T$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, $p(e_i)$ seems to represent the uncertainty in a problem and so one may ask: Why should a second uncertainty function, namely entropy, exist? We argue that $p(e_i)$ does not simply represent uncertainty, but also displays the a priori constraint used in the problem (based on the physics of the problem). Thus, if $E = \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ is conserved, one expects a linear e_i to appear in $p(e_i)$, but if $\langle E^2 \rangle$ is conserved, one expects an e_i^2 . One thus needs a method which forces such a constraint term to appear, but is based on maximization of an uncertainty function. Thus, a second uncertainty function is required. To force each $p(e_i)$ to link to its corresponding $f(e_i)$ where $f(e_i) = -e_i/T$ in the simple E conservation case, one requires this function to have the form: $\sum_i g(p(e_i))$ which may be written generally as $\sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ because $p(e_i) > 0$. The key idea for all three distributions is that $h(p(e_i))$ is linked to the constraint $f(e_i)$ through $h(p(e_i)) = -1/T f(e_i)$, forcing $f(e_i)$ to appear in the functional form of $p(e_i)$. The issue then is dealing with the term: $\sum_i p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0$

The Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases simply force the coefficient of $dp(e_i)$ to be 0 in order to force $p(e_i)$ to pick up the constraint variable $f(e_i)$. The Tsallis approach is more general. It partly forces $p(e_i)$ to pick up the constraint variable by having part of the result lead to a 0 coefficient of $dp(e_i)$, but also creates a sum term overall $dp(e_i)$'s which is 0. After all, the overall maximization problem is a sum problem and it is simplification to assume that all $dp(e_i)$ coefficients are 0 as if the $p(e_i)$'s are all independent, which they are not due to $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. This leads to an extra condition: $\sum_i (p(e_i)^k + p(e_i)^{-k}) dp(e_i) = 0$ or $\sum_i \sqrt{1+kke_i/T} dp(e_i) = 0$.